

Techno-economic optimization of the industrial excess heat recovery for an industrial park with high spatial and temporal resolution

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ABSTRACT

With increasing heating and cooling demands, decarbonisation of the heating and cooling sectors is key to achieving a carbon-neutral energy system. Using industrial excess heat in heating systems helps offset emissions by reducing the use of fossil fuels. While several studies have analysed the temperature of heat availability, the cost of extending or constructing the heating network and techno-economic feasibility, it is important to consider all aspects together to achieve a comprehensive design of industrial excess heat recovery. This study proposes a method to link an energy system optimisation tool with a spatial analysis tool and an exergy analysis tool to achieve a comprehensive design. An iterative soft link is implemented between the energy system model and the spatial analysis tool for high spatial and temporal resolution. The developed method is applied to a case study of an industrial park in Greece. Scenarios are developed to assess the robustness of the developed method and the system profitability of excess heat recovery. The scenarios indicated that the profitability of excess heat depends heavily on the price of natural gas with the share of excess heat increasing from 10% to 45% with a 20% increase in natural gas prices in cases where heat pumps are needed for temperature boosting. In cases where heat pumps are not needed, excess heat indicates higher system profitability with a share of around 40% and reduces the emissions by around 50 times. The method provides robust results in considered scenarios with convergence within four iterations.

1. Introduction

Heating and cooling demands account for half of the final energy consumption in Europe. In 2021, about 75% of heating and cooling energy in the European Union (EU) was supplied from fossil fuels as shown in Fig. 1 [1]. Gas alone accounted for 46% of heat and cold generation [1]. Given the growing need to transition to sustainable energy supply systems, the decarbonisation of heating and cooling systems is crucial to achieving EU climate targets [1]. District heating and cooling systems (DHCS) have been used to efficiently supply heating and cooling [2]. Large-scale centralised district heating systems (DHS) can contribute to the decarbonisation of the heating sector by incorporating renewable and fossil-free sources [3]. According to Werner et al. [4], the fundamental idea of district heating is to “use local fuel or heat resources that would otherwise be wasted to meet local customer heat demand by using a heat distribution network of pipes as a local marketplace.” The

developments in district heating have focused on improving energy efficiency and smart integrated energy systems, through the 4th and 5th generations of DHS. The development of 4th and 5th-generation district heating emphasises large-scale integration of industrial excess heat (IEH), geothermal heat, and solar panels [5].

Like the heating and cooling sectors, the industrial sector is also a major energy consumer in the EU. The industry accounted for 26.1% of the EU’s final energy consumption in 2020 [7]. Moreover, a large part of the emissions in the EU is generated by industrial processes. However, in these industries, part of the fossil fuel demand cannot be completely eliminated despite today’s mature technologies. The processes available for these technologies are not yet deployed on large-scale, especially when fossil fuels are used as process fuels and in high-temperature processes. Nevertheless, high-temperature processes in industry generate a large amount of excess heat (EH) that can be used to meet different types of heating and cooling demands, i.e., space heating and cooling, hot water, and process heating and cooling. In addition, the use

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Nomenclature			
CHP	Combined Heat and Power	HP	Heat Pump
DHCS	District Heating and Cooling System	IEH	Industrial Excess Heat
DHN	District Heating Network	IEHC	Industrial Excess Heat and Cold
DHS	District Heating System	L2D	Length to Diameter
EH	Excess Heat	LCOH	Levelised Cost of Heat
EHC	Excess Heat and Cold	MW	Mega Watt
EHR	Excess Heat Recovery	NECP	National Energy and Climate Plans
EMB3RS	Energy-Matching & Business Prospection Tool for Excess Heat/Cold Reduction, Recovery and Redistribution	OSeMOSYS	Open-Source Energy Modeling System
ESOM	Energy System Optimisation Model	OSM	Open Street Maps
ETS	Emission Trading System	PJ	Peta Joule
EU	European Union	TEOM	Techno-Economic Optimisation Model
GAMS	General Algebraic Modeling System	TES	Thermal Energy Storage
GIS	Geographic Information System	THERMOS	Thermal Energy Resource Modelling and Optimisation System
GW	Giga Watt	UEH	Urban Excess Heat
		UK	United Kingdom

Fig. 1. Share of fuels in heating and cooling supply in the EU in 2020 [6].

of EH from industry in heating and cooling systems can avoid direct fuel use for meeting heating and cooling demands and hence related emissions.

The recovery and utilisation of industrial excess heat (IEH) in DHS have been thoroughly analysed in other studies. Several studies have quantified excess heat potentials using geospatial mapping of IEH sources and heat demand. Forman et al. estimated global industrial EHC potential at 32 PJ in 2012 [8] and Albert et al. estimated the industrial EHC in the UK to be 46,000 GWh in 2018 [9]. Both the studies utilised geographic mapping of IEH sources and analysed the overlap with existing or potential DHS to estimate the actual potential of IEH. Manz et al. mapped the IEH potential of 1608 industrial sites in Europe and concluded that IEH use could meet up to 17% of the EU's hot water demand in 2021 [10]. The study concluded that the economic feasibility of IEH recovery and use can be expected for all industrial sites located within 2 km of DHS. Therefore, previous studies have emphasised the need to consider the distance of an EH source from the grid while analysing EH integration into DHS [11]. The use of recovered EH within the industry is an alternative to using it in DHS. However, the mapping of excess heat potential described above has indicated that there is a large potential for use of excess heat in DHS even after meeting in-house heat demands [12]. Therefore, this study focuses primarily on the use of EH in DHS.

In addition to distance from existing grids, IEH variability has been identified as one of the barriers to excess heat recovery (EHR) adoption [13]. The heat demand in DHSs is also variable. Therefore, high temporal resolution analysis is required to analyse EHR [11]. Techno-economic optimization models (TEOM) have been used in the past to analyse the integration of EH into DHSs [14]. These models also have the capability of using long and short-term configurations to overcome variability. TEOMs are used to provide insights on the least-cost medium-to-long term investment pathways for planning IEH integration and use as part of the larger supply system, with consideration of budget and resource constraints. They have the advantage of providing a quick and simple bird-view optimised picture with relatively low computational effort and easy-to-grasp algorithms. On the other side, they do not replace detailed process-simulation tools and exergy analysis which are especially useful for more detailed sizing of individual components within the network.

Besides the spatial and temporal aspects, it is also important to consider the exergy aspect. The extraction of low-quality EH for use in DHS has been presented as a major obstacle [11]. The quality of available EH is of critical importance for the development of heat recovery technologies and has a major impact on the techno-economic feasibility of EHR. Several methods such as pinch analysis, second law analysis and exergy analysis can be used to evaluate the quality of excess heat. Among these, the exergy analysis of EHR considers the mass and energy balances of the processes along with the quality of available excess heat to determine the exergy feasibility of the proposed solution. Furthermore, detailed exergy analysis can also be used to size the different components needed for EHR such as the design of heat exchangers [16]. The exergy analysis tool used in [16] designs heat exchangers for industrial EHR based on the temperature difference on the source, the logarithmic mean temperature difference (LMTD) and the heat transfer fluid.

In contrast to a macro-level energy system analysis, exergy analysis considers the temperature feasibility of EHR at the process and component level. Thus, exergy analysis yields a significantly different design of technologies and selection of sources compared to energy analysis [15] i.e., while the energy analysis seeks to cover maximum demand using EH, the use of lower temperature sources with boosting technologies would be a viable option. However, an exergy analysis would lead to the choice of higher temperature sources with heat exchangers to provide maximum exergy efficiency of the system. The two well-developed analyses have been often conducted at separate levels. This study argues that it is necessary to combine the two analyses to capture both the energy and temperature feasibility aspects of EHR.

Thus, there are three aspects, spatial considerations, excess heat

quality considerations and temporal variability considerations, that are critical for analysing EH and hence will be considered while analysing the case of IEH recovery and use in DHS. The paper is structured as follows. Section 1.1 provides the background, and section 1.2 discusses the aim of the study. Section 2 describes the methods used, Section 3 explains the case study followed by Section 4 which provides the results. Section 5 presents the discussion and Section 6 summarises the main conclusions.

1.1. Background

The potential for industrial EHR has been evaluated and established in studies. Despite the large potential for recovery of IEH and use in DHS, there have been several barriers to the implementation of industrial EHR projects. Jodeiri et al. reviewed the challenges to integrating industrial EHC into DHS and highlighted the ‘distance of heat sources from DHS, incompatibility of source temperature with grid temperature and temporal mismatch of heat availability and demand’ as major challenges [17]. This indicates the need for detailed techno-economic modelling of industrial EHC considering a high spatial and temporal resolution, and storage options.

From the perspective of the industries, studies have shown that a lack of know-how to plan and implement industrial EHR projects creates barriers [18]. Brueckner et al. analysed several methods for determining IEH potential. The study concluded that the unavailability of data and lack of know-how in the industry are the main obstacles to EHC recovery and use [19]. This has also been highlighted by Fritz et al. along with long contract periods and initial high investments as major barriers [13]. Kohne et al. have highlighted information deficits as one of the major barriers to EHR [12]. Moser et al. also emphasise the lack of information as a major roadblock [20]. The study argues that the lack of knowledge about potential EH sources and sinks leads to unknown revenue potentials. Moreover, the optimisation of processes for external heat recovery is seldom considered due to a lack of information. Schmidt et al. have classified barriers to excess heat recovery into 5 categories – ‘General, Technical, Financial, Legislative and Societal’ [11]. The study highlights a lack of know-how and awareness (general), spatial, temporal and temperature mismatch (technical), uncertainty in the long-term contracts (legislative) and additional costs (financial) as barriers to excess heat recovery.

Unwillingness to take risks due to imperfect and asymmetric information, and dependency of the industries on the DHCS operators have also been identified as other key obstacles. Kohne et al. and Moser et al. have attempted to address the lack of information by providing a heat merit order for use of excess heat internally and externally. However, the merit only indicates the excess heat profitability. The industrial stakeholders would need a concrete investment plan based on a portfolio of modelling analysis considering the different aspects of the problem [55]. The current study focuses on solving the problems of imperfect information using Energy System Optimisation Models (ESOM)s that are shown to ease the problem of imperfect information, while considering spatial, temporal and temperature mismatch to overcome the general and technical barriers for EHR. Modelling studies provide insights to the industrial stakeholders about the investment pathways for EHR. However, the industrial stakeholders must also consider that the ESOMs require data and the results of the models usually have perfect foresight based on the input data. Despite this, the initial results from ESOMs could further boost cooperation and reduce dependency on the DHCS operators [21]. Gustafsson et al. analysed the role of spatial analysis and planning as enablers of industrial EHC use in DHS [22]. The study concluded that strategic spatial planning could further boost the integration of industrial EH in DHS. The above indicates the importance of modelling industrial EHC while considering spatial and temporal aspects.

There is extensive literature on the three aspects of industrial EHR. Chambers et al. used spatial analysis to determine the feasibility of

integrating IEH in the DHS in Switzerland. A spatial clustering method is used for the mapping of DHS demands and IEH sources to determine the technical feasibility of connecting potential supply and demand points [23]. In the EU horizon 2020 project Heat Roadmap Europe (HRE), several versions of a Pan-European thermal atlas have been developed. A regional balance of excess heat relative to the heat demand for all third-level administrative regions is developed to identify strategic regions suitable for large-scale implementation of DHS. The study revealed that 46% of all EH in EU 27 and a corresponding 31% of heat demands are located within identified strategic regions [24]. Möller et al. developed the method further by adding the functionalities of estimating the techno-economic potential of district heating expansion in the heat atlas developed in HRE [25]. Grundahl et al. used the heat atlas from HRE to determine the techno-economic potential of expanding existing district heating networks (DHN)s to neighbouring towns in Denmark. The expansion potential is determined based on an economic comparison between district heating and decentralized heating systems [26].

Sandvall et al. developed a TEOM to analyse the use of urban excess heat (UEH) from various UEH sources such as data centres, metro stations, sewage systems, and buildings’ cooling systems in the DHS [27]. The study analysed how the cost of heat supply in the DHS can be reduced by the inclusion of UEH. The study concluded that the inclusion of UEH can make DHS more cost-competitive and replace individual heating systems in buildings. Sandvall et al. continued the analysis in [27] by determining the system profitability of EH utilisation in [28]. The study indicated that EH could be used to phase out natural gas from the DHS and the profitability of the system increases with the introduction of a carbon tax. While these studies have been used to conduct energy optimization by including EH in DHS, other studies have analysed the exergy aspect. However, these studies do not consider the spatial and quality aspects of excess heat.

Cunha et al. conducted a techno-economic comparison of different alternatives for the inclusion of IEH in a DHS in Portugal. A characterization algorithm was used to consider exergy aspects of IEH such as temperature, mass flow rate and heat capacities of fluids used for industrial EHR. The characterisation algorithm is used to design technologies which are compared with a portable storage alternative based on the Levelised Cost of Heat (LCOH) [16]. Fitó et al. analysed an exergy optimal design of DHS using a mixed integer linear optimisation algorithm. An exergy-based design was considered by including the quality of heat from the different streams of IEH and accounting for exergy losses at every conversion stage [15]. While TEOMs have considered an energy-based optimisation of IEH integration, considering the exergy aspect adds to the practical accuracy of the results by considering the temperature compatibility of the different technologies. However, the design of an exergy-based optimization could lead to a computationally expensive model due to the non-linearity, parallel optimisations of temperatures and mass flow rates. Thus, it is important to use the relative computational ease of using energy-based optimization while also considering exergy feasibility exogenously.

With the availability of literature on models focusing on each aspect of excess heat recovery, several methodologies for linking these models have also been developed. Zuberi et al. introduced a method for integrating spatial mapping and exergy analysis to estimate the techno-economic feasibility of EHC recovery and applied it to the Swiss industrial sector [29]. Chambers et al. developed a method for spatio-temporal analysis by including IEH in the DHS. The spatial mapping of demand and IEH sources was used to analyse the techno-economic feasibility of extending the DHN. This was complemented with a temporal energy balance at a monthly resolution to determine the potential for seasonal thermal storage [23]. Other studies have conducted a spatiotemporal analysis by linking a spatial analysis tool with an ESOM. A heat atlas has been used to calculate the costs of extending DHN to IEH sources. The costs are then input to an ESOM to conduct a cost-based optimization between using existing heat generation sources in the DHS and including IEH sources. Connolly et al. [30] applied the method

Fig. 2. Soft linking of the models.

on a European scale, while a national analysis for Denmark was conducted by Petrovic et al. [31]. In both studies, a GIS-based heat map was linked to the energy system model ‘EnergyPlan’ to include the cost of expanding DHN in the optimisation.

Studies have also linked tools to analyse at least two aspects of industrial EHR, i.e., at least two out of the three, spatial, temporal variability and excess heat quality. However, most links between the tools consider a soft linking approach, where each tool is linked with other tools through the exchange of results. The spatial expansion of the network is analysed, and the costs of the network extension are calculated which are further used in the ESOM. However, in such cases, the sizes of the new pipes and the losses in the DHN are not considered. The diameter of the pipes forms a significant part of the network extension costs. Hence, the losses in the network could determine the techno-economic feasibility. Large transmission losses could lead to the integration of the IEH source being too expensive. Furthermore, it is vital to analyse the quality of the heat for an accurate estimation of the technical potential of industrial EHR. There is little literature on methodologies or models to analyse critical aspects of the industrial EHR in a comprehensive modelling framework. This study proposes a novel method for linking special-purpose tools that address the three considered aspects of industrial EHR.

1.2. Aim

The study aims to develop a coherent modelling framework for analysing industrial EHR such that the three main aspects, i.e., spatial,

excess heat quality and temporal variability characteristics are captured and represented accurately. One of the main goals of the paper is to ensure the development of a framework where the results from each tool are compatible and coherent with the results from the other tools, such that a practical solution for EHR is designed. The paper attempts to achieve the aim by answering the below research questions:

- (1) How can special-purpose tools be used in tandem to capture three aspects of industrial EHR and provide a combined and coherent optimisation?
 - a. How do a spatial tool and an ESOM interact in a way that the investment costs of the network extension are considered along with the cost and the constraints of sizing the pipes in the network?
 - b. How to consider the temperature of IEH by using a link between an ESOM and an exergy analysis tool?

The method developed in the study uses a soft link between three special-purpose tools. An exergy analysis tool, a spatial analysis tool and an ESOM are linked together and the latter two are operated iteratively for a comprehensive analysis of the three aspects of industrial EHR. The proposed novel method is developed by linking the open-source long-term ESOM OseMOSYS (Open-source Energy Modeling System) with a spatial analysis algorithm and a characterisation-based algorithm to account for the exergy. While a hard link between the tools increases the computational requirements to a considerable extent, a single soft link fails to provide coherent results. Thus, the study proposes a soft link with an iterative operation such that the results from each special-purpose tool are coherent. This is further explained in Section 2.4. The method is applied to a real-life case study consisting of IEH sources in the industrial cluster close to the town of Agios Georgios in Greece. The recovery of IEH and the supply of the recovered heat to neighbouring DHCS and industrial sinks within the cluster are analysed using the developed modelling framework.

2. Methods

The three models are soft-linked to conduct a combined optimisation of the system as shown in Fig. 2.

Sections 2.1-2.3 provide a brief description of the functionalities of each special purpose model. Section 2.4 describes the methods to link the tools. Section 2.5 describes the case study and the application of the developed framework. The modelling framework has been developed as a part of the EMB3RS platform which is designed as a simple match-making tool that addresses the key requirements when planning a new DHN or expanding an existing DHN, focusing on the use of IEH [32]. A detailed explanation of the EMB3RS platform can be found in Appendix 1.

Fig. 3. Source conversion to the DHN when a temperature boosting technology is not required (A) and when it is required (B).

Fig. 4. DHN conversion to the sink when a temperature boosting technology is not required (A), when it is required (B) and when process cooling is required (C).

2.1. Heuristic choice of technology based on exergy analysis

The exergy analysis model analyses the conversion of IEH to useful heat that is supplied to the heat/cold consumer (sink) through the DHN. The exergy analysis tool can provide a detailed process and component analysis for internal and external heat recovery for industrial processes. For the purpose, of this study, the tool has only been used to provide technology choices for EHR that are temperature feasible. This tool determines all the technologies that can be used to convert the IEH to useful heat based on the temperature of the heat. It then provides the list of all the suitable technologies along with their techno-economic data to the ESOM. The process of choosing the conversion technology for the IEH sources is explained in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4. A third-generation DHS with a supply temperature of 100 °C and a return temperature of 70 °C is considered for this study [33].

If the EH source has a temperature higher than 120 °C, the tool considers the installation of a closed hydraulic circuit with thermal oil and a secondary circuit with water that supplies heat to the DHN as shown in Fig. 3A. Both circuits have a circulating pump. A plate heat exchanger is considered on the DHN side and a shell and tube heat exchanger, plate heat exchanger, or economizer is usually considered on the source side, depending on the existing fluid of the EH source. The intermediate circuit temperature is optimised based on the supply and return temperature in the DHN and the available and target temperature for the source. The target temperatures for the source are optimised such that maximum heat is recovered from the source. However, the method can only consider the supply and return temperature in the DHN as input and these temperatures are not optimised. This is further explained in Section 2.2.

When the temperature of the excess heat source is below the supply temperature required by the DHN, a boosting technology is used to raise the temperature. A heat exchanger on the source side is considered for EH recovery, and the boosting technology provides the required temperature to the DHN as shown in Fig. 3B. The heat sources are considered and characterised separately in the proposed methods. While the

mixing of excess heat streams within an industry is a possibility, in reality, the proposed method characterises each stream separately in its current status. Thus, this part of the method can be improved to consider an optimal mixing of streams within the industry.

The conversion from DHN to sink can be summarized in Fig. 4 depending on the sink requirements (process heat, process steam, and process cooling). Similar to source conversion, the exergy analysis tool considers a plate heat exchanger and circulating pump if the required sink supply temperature is below the DHN supply temperature as shown in Fig. 4A. If the required temperature is above the DHN supply temperature, boosting technologies such as a heat pump is considered as shown in Fig. 4B. If process cooling is required, the installation of an absorption chiller is considered, as shown in Fig. 4C.

Apart from the conversions illustrated in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4, the tool also provides other technology solutions such as Organic Rankine Cycle (ORC) and boilers. The circuits for these have been illustrated in Appendix 2.

For both source and sink conversions, the exergy analysis tool then calculates the maximum available capacity of the source to feed into the DHN or that the DHN can provide to the sink. The exergy analysis tool provides the ESOM with the following variables: maximum capacity (in kW of heat provided to the DHN/sink), conversion efficiency (from excess heat into the DHN/from the DHN into the sink), CAPEX (in €/kW of heat provided), fixed annual O&M cost (€/kW of heat provided to the DHN/sink), variable O&M cost (€/MWh of heat provided to the DHN/sink), and CO₂ emissions (kgCO₂/MWh of heat provided to the DHN/sink). The CO₂ emissions calculated by the exergy analysis tool are associated with the use of electricity and other fuels in circulation pumps and boosting technologies, No CO₂ emissions are associated with the EH source.

The suitable technologies determined by the exergy analysis tool are further assessed using an ESOM to determine the cost-optimal technology mix. The standalone version of the exergy analysis tool and the corresponding documentation is provided on GitHub [26,27].

Fig. 5. Illustration of the modelling process in the spatial analysis tool.

2.2. Spatial analysis model

The spatial analysis model analyses the network dimension and brings the spatial dimension between EH sources and sinks into the overall modelling framework. The main functionalities of the spatial analysis module are pipe routing, thermal loss, and network cost calculation.

The spatial analysis model is a network optimisation model that considers the analysis region, heat sources and sinks, as well as economic and environmental factors like investment costs, and ground and ambient temperatures [34]. The network solution is determined using a road network graph retrieved from Open Street Maps (OSM) [35]. Every road segment of the OSM network represents a potential path for the installation of a pipe. It is possible to add new road elements, restrict or force the use of roadways, and add an existing grid network.

The spatial analysis tool can only consider water-based heating networks that are mostly used in DHS. Network based on steam, thermal oil and other higher-temperature fluids is not considered by the tool. Furthermore, the supply and return temperatures are input into the tool. These temperatures are considered by the tool to calculate pipe diameters and thermal losses in the network. It is possible to run several scenarios considering different supply and return temperatures to analyse the effect of temperature change on the recovered excess heat. Another possible extension of the tool and the method would be to optimise the supply and return temperatures in the DHN according to the source and sink temperatures. However, this should be considered for future studies.

The spatial analysis model consists of two mixed integer linear programming models as shown in Fig. 5. The main goal of the models is to minimise the length of the grid while connecting all sources and sinks and matching their heat exchange capacities. The models try to use the

existing grid (if any) as much as possible and then expand these existing pipes if their capacities are insufficient. The optimisation output is the least-distance grid network, including the lengths and capacities of each pipe. The capacities of the pipes are converted into diameters, and the thermal losses and network costs are calculated. The capacities of the pipes are not optimised directly by the spatial analysis model, but these are calculated based on the optimised dispatch provided by the energy system optimisation. This is described in Section 2.4. The optimisation of the network distance (which has the largest share in the capital costs) along with the design of pipe diameters based on optimal dispatch leads to a least-cost network solution from the modelling framework.

Network costs consist of digging and piping costs. Two surface classes are considered to reflect the digging cost differences between different surfaces: street and terrain. The piping costs are independent of surface type. Thermal losses are also calculated based on the type of pipes, namely surface and underground pipes. The ambient or underground temperatures are used depending on the type of pipe.

Outputs of the spatial analysis model are the individual and cumulative pipe lengths, losses, installed pipe capacities, the network costs between source-sink pairs, and a graphical representation of the network solution.

The spatial analysis tool does not consider the time dimension on its own. When the spatial analysis model is run for the first time, it performs the calculations for a single time step. Therefore, it works with the maximum capacities of sources and sinks. To bring in the time dimension and increase the accuracy, iteration between the spatial analysis model and ESOM is designed. In the first run, the spatial analysis model gets coordinates and heat exchange capacities of sources and sinks from the exergy analysis model. It gets heat exchange capacities of sources and sinks from the ESOM in the subsequent runs. This is further discussed in Section 2.4. The standalone version of the spatial analysis tool and the corresponding documentation can be found on GitHub [34].

2.3. Energy system optimization model

An ESOM is used to conduct optimisation of the energy system while considering the energy balance, capacity, and operating constraints of the technologies. In this study, the long-term energy system optimisation model OSeMOSYS is used for energy system optimisation. OSeMOSYS is an open-source energy system model generator that optimises long-term investments and the operation of energy and resource systems. OSeMOSYS is formulated as a linear program that dynamically computes the least-cost investment and dispatch options for each year within a defined time domain (usually of several years or decades), to meet exogenously defined demands [36]. The tool conducts a cost optimization from a societal perspective and minimises the overall net present system costs. Therefore, this study analyses the inclusion of EH from a system perspective and does not analyse the profit for each stakeholder. Several other ESOMs can consider objectives apart from cost such as optimising emission reduction. Some ESOMs also consider multi-objective optimisation, i.e., optimising costs and emissions simultaneously. However, for this study, cost optimisation within OSeMOSYS is considered. The source code of OSeMOSYS is available in various modelling languages, GNU mathprog, GAMS, and in the PULP and Pyomo packages in python [37]. For this study, the PULP-based python version of OSeMOSYS called ‘OSeMOSYS PULP’ is used [38].

OSeMOSYS is used to optimise investments in technologies for industrial EHR and the operation of these technologies. Therefore, the main objective of the optimization module is to minimize the total cost as given in Eq. (1). The exergy analysis tool determines the possible list of technologies based on temperature compatibility as described in Section 2.1. The techno-economic data for the technologies is input to OSeMOSYS to determine the cost-optimal technology capacity and operation. The techno-economic data is obtained from an open-source database further explained in Section 2.6.

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{Totalcost} = & \sum_{\text{year}} \left\{ \sum_{\text{Technology}} (\text{Discounted technology investment costs} \right. \\
& - \text{Technology Salvage value} \\
& + \text{Discounted technology operating costs} \\
& \left. + \text{Discounted technology emission penalties} \right\} \\
& + \left\{ \sum_{\text{Storage}} (\text{Discounted storage investment costs} \right. \\
& \left. - \text{Storage salvage value} \right\} \quad (1)
\end{aligned}$$

While the tool can model most elements of heating systems, the storage equations in OSeMOSYS PULP do not represent the operation of tank-based Thermal Energy Storage (TES), i.e., the storage equations do not capture temperature losses from the thermal storage. Furthermore, the original storage equations in OSeMOSYS are designed for long-term storage and thereby do not capture the dynamics of a tank-based TES. Thus, a new set of equations has been added to the OSeMOSYS PULP to enhance the tool's capability to represent TES. The conventional storage equations in OSeMOSYS PULP were first replaced with the alternative storage equation proposed by Niet et al. [39]. These equations provide a timestep-based representation of storage operation as shown below.

Sets and indices

The equations added into the OSeMOSYS code are based on various sets that form the structure of the optimisation model. Thus, it is important to define the sets before describing the equations.

$\forall s \in S$ – 'S' represents the set of all storages.

$\forall y \in Y$ – 'Y' represents the set of all years.

$\forall t \in T$ – 'T' represents the set of all intra-annual timesteps.

Equations:

$$E_{y,s,t} = \begin{cases} S_{l,y} = S_y & \forall s \in S, y \\ E_{y,s,t-1} + \sum_{t=1}^{8760} E_{chr,s,t,y-1} - E_{dis,s,t,y-1} - E_{loss,s,t,y-1}, y \neq S_y & \forall s \in S, y \\ \in Y, t \in T \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Eq. (2) describes the starting level of the storage at the beginning of the year. 'S' represents the set of all storages, $E_{y,s,t}$ describes the stored energy in storage 's' in the first timestep of the year 'y'. If the considered year is the first year of storage operation, S_y , in the modelling period, then the start level is defined by an input parameter or starting storage level, S_l . If the considered year is not the start year, the starting level is determined based on the storage operation in the previous year. $E_{chr,s,t,y-1}$ and $E_{dis,s,t,y-1}$ indicate the charging and discharging of storage 's', in timestep 't' and year 'y' respectively.

$$E_{t,s,y} = \begin{cases} E_{y,s,t}, t = 1 \\ E_{t,s,y-1} + E_{chr,s,t,y-1} - E_{dis,s,t,y-1} - E_{loss,s,t,y-1}, t > 1 \end{cases} \forall s \in S, y \in Y, t \in T \quad (3)$$

Eq. (3) describes the starting level of the storage at each timestep of the year. $E_{t,s,y}$ describes the starting level of storage 's' in each timestep 't' in each year 'y'. The $E_{t,s,y}$ for the first timestep is equal to the $E_{y,s,t}$ calculated in Eq. (2). $E_{t,s,y}$ in every subsequent timestep 't' is determined based on the storage operation and the storage losses in the timestep 't-1'. $E_{loss,s,t,y}$ indicates the thermal losses from storage 's', in timestep 't' and in year 'y'.

In addition to the above equations representing the storage operation, the capacity of the storage is determined and constrained using the below equations. Eq (4)–(7) which were also proposed by Niet et al. [39].

$$E_{t,s,y} \leq \text{Cap}_{sto,s,y} \quad (4)$$

$$E_{t,s,y} \geq E_{min,s,y} * \text{Cap}_{sto,s,y} \quad (5)$$

$$\text{Cap}_{sto,s,y} \leq \text{Maxcap}_{sto,s,y} \quad (6)$$

Eq. (4) ensures that the $\text{Cap}_{sto,s,y}$ which represents the installed capacity for storage 's' in year 'y' is greater than the storage level in any timestep 't'. A minimum and maximum storage level is always maintained by setting the $E_{min,s,y}$ and $\text{Maxcap}_{sto,s,y}$ in Eqs. (5) and (6) respectively. The capital costs for the storage are accounted for as below.

$$\text{Capex}_{sto,s,y} \geq \text{Capcost}_{sto,s,y} * \text{Cap}_{sto,s,y} \quad (7)$$

Eq. (7) calculates $\text{Capex}_{sto,s,y}$ which is the capital investment of each storage 's' in year 'y' based on the specific capital cost, $\text{Capcost}_{sto,s,y}$ and the installed capacity of storage, $\text{Cap}_{sto,s,y}$.

Further, a temperature-based representation of losses from the storage has been added to OSeMOSYS. The heat transfer equation for convection is used as a starting point to design these equations. The generic heat transfer equation is illustrated in Eq. (8).

$$Q_{loss} = U_{sto} * SA_{sto} * \Delta T \quad (8)$$

U_{sto} is the heat transfer coefficient in kW/m²K, SA_{sto} is the storage surface area in m² and ΔT is the difference between the storage temperature and the ambient temperature in Kelvin. Since the ESOM optimises the storage capacity (in energy units), the storage surface area must be related to the storage capacity to capture the losses. However, the storage surface area has a nonlinear relation with the storage capacity as shown in Eqs. (9) and (10).

$$D_{sto} = \left(\frac{\text{Cap}_{sto}}{\Delta T * C_p} \right)^{1/3} \quad (9)$$

$$SA_{sto} = \left(\frac{\pi * D_{sto}^2}{2} \right) + (\pi * D_{sto} * H_{sto}) \quad (10)$$

Here, D_{sto} is the storage diameter in metres, H_{sto} is the storage height in metres and C_p is the specific heat capacity of water in kWh/kgK.

The relationship is linearized using linear regression for storage capacities in the range of 1 to 5000 MWh. The relationship also depends on the storage length to diameter (L2D) ratio, which defines the orientation of the TES tank. Thus, two L2D ratios, 1 and 2 are considered for this equation, since these two ratios have been shown to have the least temperature losses in previous studies [40]. Based on the regression, the below equations are added. The data and the graphs used for the linear regression are explained in Appendix 2.

$$SA_{sto,s,y} = \begin{cases} 1.5374 * \text{Cap}_{sto,s,y}, L2D = 1 \\ 2.7673 * \text{Cap}_{sto,s,y}, L2D = 2 \end{cases} \forall s \in S, y \in Y, t \quad (11)$$

Finally, the storage losses are calculated based on Eq. (12). The temperature level in the storage depends on the state of charge of the storage. However, since the model also calculates the storage capacities, calculating the state of charge which is a ratio of the storage level to the storage capacity, would lead to nonlinearity. Therefore, an average of the supply and return temperature of the storage is used to calculate the losses. Although this leads to small inaccuracies in the storage losses, significant computational complications would be needed to consider a mixed integer-based approach to represent losses as a function of the state of charge.

$$E_{loss,s,y,t} = U_{sto,s,y,t} * SA_{sto,s,y,t} * \left\{ \left(\frac{\text{ST}_{sto,s} + \text{RT}_{sto,s}}{2} \right) - \text{AT}_{sto,s} \right\} \quad (12)$$

$\text{ST}_{sto,s}$ is the storage supply temperature in °C, $\text{RT}_{sto,s}$ storage return temperature in °C and $\text{AT}_{sto,s}$ is the ambient. The temperature in °C. Eqs. (8)–(11) present a temperature-based representation of thermal storage operation and the losses.

The main results of the techno-economic optimization are the cost-

Fig. 6. Main outputs and inputs of each tool.

optimal capacities and the heat generated from these technologies. The model thus determines the cost-optimal exchange of heat between the various sources and sinks which is used to design the DHN in the spatial analysis tool. This is further discussed in Section 2.4. The standalone version of ESOM and the corresponding documentation can be found on GitHub [41].

2.4. Linking of the models and the data transfer

This study proposes an iterative soft link between the three models for a comprehensive and coherent analysis of IEH recovery and integration into DHS. The iterative link establishes the coherence between the results from each module, thereby ensuring a sound design of technologies for industrial EHR.

The main outputs of each model and the data transfer between the models are shown in Fig. 6. The colour code in Fig. 6 indicates the data transfer between the models. The box under each model indicates the main outputs of the model. The colour of the boxes with the outputs that match the colour of the box with the model names indicates the inputs to the model.

The sequence of operations is as below

Step 1: The exergy model is first operated to determine the maximum possible capacities of industrial EHR based on temperature compatibility and the suitable technologies for industrial EHR.

Step 2: The second step in the operation requires careful consideration since both the ESOM and the spatial model depend on each other's outputs for optimization. To resolve the issue, in the first iteration, the network is designed based on the maximum possible capacities for every IEH source and heat sink. This solution considers all possible connections between the sources and the sinks in the DHN. The network is designed based on the maximum exchange capacities and the losses and the capital costs of the network are calculated. Therefore, in the first iteration, the presented network solution has low accuracy, and this will be refined in the next iteration by using actual capacities determined by the ESOM.

Step 3: ESOM determines the least cost matching of sources and sinks based on the set of possible technologies provided by the exergy analysis tool while considering the energy losses in the network. The least cost solution considers both the capital and operating costs of the technologies at the sources and the sinks. Since the loss values from the spatial analysis tool are given as power losses (in kW), these losses are added using an additional constraint for each hour. The additional constraint in the ESOM forces the DHN to consume more energy each hour. Based on this, the maximum exchange between the IEH sources and the heat sinks is calculated. The exchange capacities indicate the hourly heat flow from each source to each sink in the network. The results from ESOM are passed onto the spatial analysis model for the next iterations.

Step 4: In the second iteration (and up to the nth), the spatial analysis

tool uses the calculated maximum exchange capacities to determine more accurate losses and the investment costs of the DHN. Based on the hourly exchange capacities, the pipe capacities are adjusted, and the corresponding losses are updated.

Step 5: The corrected network losses and costs are fed to the ESOM, which then determines again the least-cost capacities and dispatch of excess heat between the sources and sinks.

Step 6: The maximum exchange capacities for ESOM are once again input to the spatial analysis tool to start the next iteration.

The network losses determined by the spatial analysis tool are used as a decision variable for the iterations. The losses in the network lead to the correction of the industrial EHR capacities and thus the design of the technology mix. A threshold of 1% for the variation in the losses between consecutive iterations is used as the criteria for convergence. The sequence of operations in iterations is shown in Fig. 7.

The data transfer between the models can either be done manually while using the standalone version of each model. Alternatively, the models have also been soft-linked in a single python script which can also be used to run the simulations [42].

3. Case study

The methods described in Section 2 are applied to a real-life industrial case study. The case study refers to the Volos Industrial Park, located near the town of Agios Georgios in Greece. In the industrial park, there are six industries that need process heat at different temperatures as shown in Table 2. The requirement of process heat is split into different streams based on the temperature. The process heat requirements are currently being met by using natural gas boilers. In the industrial park, four potential excess heat sources- flue gas from a biomass plant, flue gas from the exhaust of a plastic polymerisation plant, exhaust air from the limestone grinding plant, and flue gas from a steel plant have been identified. Furthermore, there is also demand for space heating, hot water heating and space cooling in the neighbouring town of Agios Georgios. The reference energy system (RES) of the case is shown in Fig. 8.

The EH from the industries in the Volos industrial part could be used to supply the process heat in the industrial sinks and heating for space and hot water heating and cooling. Connecting the sources and sinks of heat through a new DHS could facilitate the recovery and use of IEH, reducing the use of the natural gas-based heating system and thereby decreasing emissions related to heat generation.

The owners of IEH sources in the Volos industrial park are interested in knowing how much excess heat could be recovered and sold if their plants were to be connected to DHS. The method described in Section 2 is applied to estimate a) the potential for linking the industrial sources and sinks through a new DHN, b) the quantity of excess heat that could be used in the network, and c) the emissions saved.

Fig. 7. Sequence of operation of the different models.

Table 1
Case study data - Sources.

Number	Supply temperature (°C)	Target temperature (°C)	Capacity (kW)	Fluid
Source 1	220	120	4340	Flue gas
Source 2	70	30	2790	Water
Source 3	180	120	890	Flue gas
Source 4	900	500	2436	Flue gas

The case is analysed both from the perspective of the industrial stakeholder by determining the most profitable investment for the industries and from the perspective of the policymakers to analyse the

policy incentives needed to promote the inclusion of IEH in the system.

Due to the higher cost of temperature-boosting technologies, the process heat required by the industrial sinks is divided into the heat required to preheat the feed water to 95 °C and the remaining heat required to generate process steam. The information about the sources and sinks in the case is summarised in Table 1 and Table 2. Some sinks need heat at different temperatures for different processes. The different processes are represented as different streams in Table 2.

For the sinks with steam as the fluid, the feedwater is vaporised into steam and then heated up to the required temperature.

However, the design of the case study leads to exergy losses within the EHR system. The range of temperatures needed in the sinks with heating needs varies between 180 °C and 64 °C. The source temperatures also vary between 900 °C and 70 °C. However, the DHN is considered to operate between 100 °C and 70 °C. This leads to a large-

Table 2
Case study data - Sinks.

Number	Required temperature (°C)	Available temperature (°C)	Capacity (kW)	Fluid	Annual demand (GWh)	
					2022	2032
Sink 1 Stream 1	180	95	815	steam	2.99	2.99
Sink 1 Stream 2	95	10	79	water	0.30	0.30
Sink 2 Stream 1	180	95	781	steam	1.28	1.28
Sink 2 Stream 2	95	10	76	water	0.13	0.13
Sink 3 Stream 1	180	95	260	steam	1.51	1.51
Sink 3 Stream 2	95	10	25	water	0.15	0.15
Sink 4 Stream 1	80	10	250	water	2.19	2.19
Sink 4 Stream 2	175	10	1250	steam	10.15	10.15
Sink 4 Stream 3	90	10	138	water	1.21	1.21
Sink 5 Stream 1	180	64	2777	steam	4.91	4.91
Sink 5 Stream 2	64	10	231	water	0.42	0.42
Sink 6 Stream 1	164	95	1539	steam	13.16	13.16
Sink 6 Stream 2	95	10	153	water	1.34	1.34
Sink 7 Stream 1	60	10	596	water	1.31	1.31
Sink 7 Stream 2	7	12	497	water	0.05	0.055
Sink 7 Stream 3	80	60	480	water	0.37	0.41

Fig. 8. Reference energy system of the case study.

Fig. 9. Destruction of exergy due to considered temperatures.

scale destruction of exergy at the source side due to a reduction in temperature. The temperature is then boosted on the sink side using heat pumps. The process is described in Fig. 9.

To avoid the large-scale destruction of exergy, an alternate solution of considering a steam network within the industrial park could be considered. All sinks with temperature needs of above grid supply temperature of 100 °C need steam. This could be provided by using heat recovery steam generators at high-temperature sources and a steam network within the industrial park as shown in Fig.10.

Comparing the source and sink capacities from Table 1 and Table 2,

the source capacities are significantly higher than the sink capacities considering both hot water and steam demands. Therefore, the solution proposed in Fig. 10 is technically feasible. However, the design and optimisation of a steam network are outside the scope of the developed method and hence this solution cannot be modelled using the modelling framework described in this study. Therefore, to eliminate the effect of the large-scale exergy destruction, a secondary case is run only with sinks with hot water demand from Table 2.

3.1. Input data

The three modules in the developed framework have different inputs. Some of these inputs of one module are obtained from the other modules through the iterative links, while other inputs are provided exogenously. The exergy analysis model uses the supply temperature, the target temperature, the fluid, and the maximum capacity of the sources and sink as shown in Table 3. The capacity and the location of each source and sink are input to the spatial analysis tool. The ESOM obtains the data regarding the possible technologies for each source and sinks from the exergy analysis tool. The capital costs and losses from the network are provided to the ESOM by the spatial analysis tool. For each technology chosen by the exergy analysis tool, the techno-economic characteristics

Fig. 10. Alternate solution with steam network.

Table 3
Techno-economic parameters of technologies [43].

Parameter	Global conversion efficiency (%)	Capital cost (£/kW)	Fixed operation & maintenance cost (£/kW)	Variable operation & maintenance cost (£/MWh)
Hot water Boiler	80.54	1307.2(supply capacity) ^{0.432}	1.95	1.1
Condensing boilers	97.15	164.3(supply capacity) ^{0.8265}	1.95	1.1
Steam boilers	89.45	1307.6(supply capacity) ^{0.5484}	1.95	1.1
Heat Pumps	0.55*(supply temperature + 273 + 5)/	1307.6(supply capacity) ^{0.5484}	2	10.9
Vapour Compression Chillers	(supply temperature - source temperature + 10)	967.53(supply capacity) ^{0.5484}	2.1	821
Absorption Chillers	40.5*(supply temperature + 273 + 5)/(source temperature -supply temperature + 10)	967.53(supply capacity) ^{0.5484}	2.2	5.5
Combined heat and power	82.66	10492(supply capacity) ^{0.7405}	10	95.8
Solar Thermal	NA	140.52(collector area) ^{1.2069}	0.01	0.067
Heat exchanger	95.2	10000 + 88(heat transfer area)	1	1
Waste heat recovery boilers	95.3	1028.2(supply capacity) ^{0.707}	1	1
Organic Rankine Cycle	81.4	24383(supply capacity) ^{0.6662}	22.7	2

Table 4
Fuel properties.

Energy carrier	CO ₂ emissions [kgCO ₂ /kWh]	Cost [€/MWh]
Natural Gas	0.209	50
Fuel Oil (average)	0.266	129.2
Biomass	0	50
Electricity	0.662	115

Table 5
Thermal Energy Storage (TES) properties.

Parameter	Unit	Value
Turnkey cost	€ / MWh	3805.4
Height to Diameter Ratio	–	2
U value of wall	W/m ² K	0.22
Supply temperature	°C	100
Return temperature	°C	70

Table 6
Scenarios overview.

Scenario number	Name	Brief description
1	<i>Reference Scenario</i>	A reference scenario of using existing heating and cooling systems is considered to calculate the current costs and emissions
2	<i>Only IEH</i>	A case of using EHR to completely replace the existing systems is used to compare the potential emissions reduction by using the EHR and the corresponding cost.
3	<i>IEH vs Reference</i>	The profitability of EHR is analysed by creating a scenario where the EHR technologies directly compete with the existing technologies for heat and cold supply for the different sinks
4	<i>Emissions Penalty</i>	This scenario considers emission penalties on all technologies apart from EHR technologies to incentivise the use of EH.
5	<i>Subsidy</i>	This scenario considers subsidies for investments in excess heat to incentivise industries to invest in EHR technologies

are obtained based on a database constructed based on literature, component factsheets and catalogues [43]. The techno-economic parameters for the technologies are shown in Table 3.

The non-linear capital costs and conversion efficiencies are linearised by the exergy analysis tool based on the maximum capacity of the sources and the sinks. For solar thermal and heat exchangers, the exergy analysis tool calculates the collector area and the heat exchanger area respectively. These are then used to calculate the capital costs for these technologies. The prices and emission factors of the fuels that are considered for this case are specified in Table 4. The emission factor for biomass is assumed to be zero for this study. The emissions associated with the cultivation and transportation of biomass are not considered within the scope of the study [44]. The emissions from the electricity grid in Greece are considered in the study since the electricity would be used by the heat pumps.

3.2. Model structure and assumptions

Temporal resolution and model horizon

To capture the variability of the IEH, the techno-economic optimisation is conducted at an hourly time resolution. 8784 intraannual timesteps are used since a leap year has been confirmed. The spatial optimisation is also conducted at a high resolution thereby considering all existing roads (except for highways or freeways) and paths in the selected project area. Due to the high time resolution, the number of years considered is kept small to reduce the computational requirements. The model horizon of ten years is modelled as two

representative years. i.e., the starting year of 2022, and a future year of 2032. The year 2032 is considered to analyse an increased demand and how the changes in future affect the IEH recovery. The years have been included in the same model, however, all connections between the years, for example, storage level have been removed, by forcing the storage to discharge all energy at the end of the year.

Discount rate

A discount factor of 4% is considered for all investments. The discount factor is used to annualise the investment costs of the technologies over their operational lifetime. The operational lifetime of each technology is input into the model.

Emissions and emission penalties

Furthermore, the plans for the electricity system in terms of reducing the carbon intensity of the electricity grid are also incorporated. These are based on Greece's national energy and climate plans (NECP) [45]. According to Greece's NECP, the emission from EU Emission Trading System (ETS) sectors will be reduced by 74% in 2030 compared to 2005 [45]. Extrapolating these goals, it is assumed that the reduction will be 76% by 2032. The emission intensity of the electricity grid was 914.5 gCO₂/kWh_{el} in 2005 [46]. Based on this, the emission intensity in 2032 is estimated to be 256 gCO₂/kWh.

Demand

While energy efficiency measures have reduced the energy needs in industries significantly, the effect is balanced out due to the expansion of industrial activities. Industries are one of the fastest-growing sectors with a growth rate of over 12% per year ref. Therefore, the demand for process heat in the industries is assumed to be constant in this study. The increase in the space heating demand is largely due to the new connections to the DHS due to a projected increase in the population [47]. However, better insulation in buildings is expected to reduce the demand further. Studies considering the future DH demands have dealt with the balance between increasing connections and insulation in different ways. The assumptions in the current study are based on the method in Connolly et al. where a demand projection was made for the EU27 [48]. While the growth rate of the population is similar to that in EU27, the number of buildings with thermal insulation in buildings is much lower, with more than 50% of the buildings built before thermal insulation was made mandatory [49]. Thus, despite Connolly et al. projecting a reduction in the space heating demand in EU27, due to the low implementation rates of thermal insulation in Greece, the space heating for the case study demand is assumed to grow by 2% between 2022 and 2032. The water heating demand is assumed to increase by 10% due to the increased number of connections. The cooling demand is also assumed to increase by 10% both due to increased number of connections and increase demand due to higher temperatures [49].

Thermal energy storage

Due to the high variability of the IEH and the constant requirement of heat demand in the industrial sinks, TES tank is also considered for the case. A hot water tank-based centralized TES is considered to be connected to the heating grid. The properties of a hot water tank-based TES are shown in Table 5.

The grid designed by the spatial model is assumed to have a supply temperature of 100 °C and a return temperature of 70 °C, considering a 3rd generation DHS [33].

3.3. Scenario development

The considered case study of the Volos Industrial Park, located near the town of Agios Georgios in Greece presents numerous options for EHR and use as indicated in Table 6. The case considers the use of recovered EH both in the industrial sinks and in the DHCS in Agios Georgios town. A new DHCS is proposed based on recovered excess heat to provide hot water and heating and cooling for the buildings in the town. Some backup technologies are included in the model to support the EH. The use of IEH is prioritised and backup technologies are only used in a case where the heat from the IEH sources is inadequate to meet the demand.

Fig. 11. Scenario development.

Table 7
Techno-economic characteristics of existing technologies.

Technology	Fixed cost [€/kW]	Efficiency
Natural gas steam boiler	1.95	0.89
Natural gas water boiler	1.95	0.92
Electric chiller	2	8.05

Table 8
Technologies chosen by exergy analysis tool for IEH.

Source/Sink	Stream	Possible technologies
Source 1	Stream 1	Heat exchanger Organic Rankine cycle
Source 2	Stream 1	Heat Pump Biomass boiler
Source 3	Stream 1	Heat exchanger
Source 4	Stream 1	Heat exchanger Organic Rankine cycle
Backup		Biomass Boiler Heat Pump
Sink 1	Stream 1 Stream 2	Heat Pump Heat exchanger
Sink 2	Stream 1 Stream 2	Heat Pump Heat exchanger
Sink 3	Stream 1 Stream 2	Heat Pump Heat exchanger
Sink 4	Stream 1 Stream 2 Stream 3	Heat exchanger Heat Pump Heat exchanger
Sink 5	Stream 1 Stream 2	Heat Pump Heat exchanger
Sink 6	Stream 1 Stream 2	Heat Pump Heat exchanger
Sink 7	Stream 1 Stream 2 Stream 3	Heat exchanger Heat exchanger Heat exchanger Absorption Chiller

Table 9
Carbon taxes in Greece [50].

Sector	Carbon tax (€/Ton CO ₂)
Natural gas in the industry	50
Natural gas in households	116
Electricity	31

Backup technologies consist of boilers, Combined Heat and Power (CHP) plants and heat pumps. These are conventional heat generation plants, which use biomass, natural gas, or electricity as fuel.

The scenarios are briefly described in Table 6 and are explained in detail in Sections 2.7.1–2.7.5. The comparison between the reference and the ‘Industrial excess heat’ is used to create further scenarios. Fig. 11 illustrates the scenario design tree.

3.3.1. Reference scenario

The reference case of existing technologies considers natural gas boilers to be used in all the sinks to satisfy the heating demand and electric chillers to provide cooling. Since the technologies are already installed, the capital costs are sunk. Thus, only the techno-economic parameters of the technologies, the fuel costs, and the emission factors are considered for this scenario. Based on the fluid required by the sink, either hot water boilers or steam boilers are used. Natural gas boilers are used for providing steam and hot water, while electric chillers are used for cooling. The technology and its techno-economic characteristics are shown in Table 7. These technologies are assumed to have enough residual capacity to meet the demand throughout the modelling period.

3.3.2. Only industrial excess heat scenario

The ‘Only IEH’ scenario considers only using the EH from the sources and backup technologies (if needed) to meet the heating and cooling demand in the sinks. The backup technologies are assigned high variable costs to ensure the operation only as a backup. The exergy analysis tool provides the set of feasible technologies and the corresponding capacities for each source and sink. The techno-economic data for the technologies and the fuels are described in Table 3. The technologies chosen by the exergy analysis tool are specified in Table 8. The choice of technology is mainly determined by the temperature of available IEH and the required temperature for heat demand.

These technologies on the source and sink side and the demand specified in Table 2 are the main inputs for the scenario. The spatial analysis tool designs the network and iterations are used to determine the cost-optimal system design.

3.3.3. Industrial excess heat vs reference scenario

This scenario will consider competition between the IEH technologies and the existing technologies to determine the system profitability of using EHR for heating and cooling. The technologies in the ‘Reference scenario’ and the ‘Industrial excess heat’ are considered for this scenario. A key assumption for this scenario is that the natural gas boilers are modelled to have enough residual capacity throughout the modelling period to meet the heat demand, thereby no new investments in natural gas boilers are needed. This assumption applies to other scenarios built based on this scenario. The technologies for industrial EHR need new investments and thus the cost-effectiveness of these investments is compared with the variable costs of the existing technologies in the cost optimization.

3.3.4. Emissions penalty scenario

This scenario is built based on the ‘IEH vs Reference’ scenario. The existing technologies consist of natural gas boilers which have a high emission factor. This scenario explores the introduction of a carbon tax to make the IEH a cheaper alternative to the existing natural gas-based heating systems. Although there are some emissions associated with the processes that lead to the generation of EH, this study considers zero emissions from EHR since the EH would be wasted or cooled off if not recovered. The carbon tax is introduced in the model from the ‘IEH vs Reference’ scenario. The current taxes on the use of natural gas in industries and households are used as an input as shown in Table 9 [50]. The carbon taxes are input to the ESOM to determine the system profitability of the excess heat under this scenario. The carbon tax rate for the industries is based on the EU ETS emissions allowances.

3.3.5. Subsidy scenario

This scenario is also built based on the ‘IEH vs Reference’ scenario. Like the emissions penalty scenario, this scenario also aims to determine the system profitability of EHR implementation when incentives are provided. It is assumed that the capital costs for the technologies to implement EHR will be reduced by 50% through a subsidy. The 50% value for subsidy is based on previous policies in various countries to incentivize green technologies. Investment subsidies via multilateral

Table 10
Inputs for sensitivity analysis.

Sensitivity parameter	Carbon tax (€/Ton CO ₂)		
	Emissions Penalty	100% increase	200 % increase
Natural gas in Industry	50.1	100.2	150.4
Natural gas in Households	115.7	231.4	347
Electricity	31.3	62.5	93.8
Sensitivity parameter	Natural gas price(€/MWh)		
	Emissions	Average	High
	Penalty		
Natural gas price	50	100	250

funding sources have also been used to offset capital costs between 12 and 90% in previous cases [51]. The value of 50% is derived as an average from the implemented cases of investment support. The capital costs of all technologies presented in Table 3 are reduced by 50% to incentivize investments in EHR.

3.4. Sensitivity analysis

A sensitivity analysis is conducted for the parameters associated with the operational costs of the technologies and the emission penalties. The sensitivity analysis is conducted based on the prices of natural gas and the future taxes on carbon in Greece. In this case, natural gas boilers are used for providing heating. The price of natural gas could change the relative profitability of using EHR. In the scenarios, a low natural gas price of 50 €/MWh is used. This is derived from the average price of natural gas in the last quarter of 2021. However, there has been a substantial increase in gas prices through 2022. Thus, variation in natural gas prices is considered for the sensitivity analysis. The average price of gas in 2022 has been around 100 €/MWh, while the highest price is around 250 €/MWh [52]. Considering the high uncertainty around future gas prices in Europe, these two prices are considered to evaluate the sensitivity of the results.

The future carbon taxes in Greece is also considered for the sensitivity analysis. The country's NECP aims to introduce a renewable energy share of 43% in the heating and cooling sector by 2030. This will be achieved by incentivising the introduction of sources of EH. Thus, for sensitivity, the current carbon tax on natural gas for process and space

heating is increased by 100% and 200% as shown in Table 10.

4. Results

This section describes the results from the designed scenarios and the subsequent sensitivity analysis. The section will mainly focus on the system-wide results, i.e., the ones provided by the ESOM. While the results are based on the functioning of the different models in the multi-model framework and indicate the importance of the links, other specific results as well as methodological insights regarding the geospatial and exergy analysis tool are detailed in separate publications. The main results from the exergy analysis tool, i.e., the choice of technologies are presented in Table 8. The design of the network from the geospatial analysis is briefly presented in Section 3.2.

4.1. Scenario results

The results of the different scenarios are presented in this section. The IEH and existing technologies scenarios are first compared with each other. Since these two scenarios model the two options separately, a comparison of the results is presented.

4.1.1. Comparison of the results of Reference and only IEH scenarios

The following section presents the comparison between the costs and emissions of using IEH with that of using existing technologies. Fig. 12 shows the emissions and the costs from the existing technologies for heat and cold supply in the different sinks.

It is interesting to note that the emission from the use of excess heat in both cases is nearly the same as using natural gas-based systems. Since most sinks use heat pumps while using excess heat, all the emissions are generated from the use of electricity which is mostly based on coal power plants. Hence, the reduction in emissions from the integration of industrial EHR depends, to a substantial extent, on the emissions from the electricity grid. This has further been investigated through a sensitivity analysis. The costs of implementing EH technologies are much higher due to the extra investment costs and the costs of electricity for running the heat pumps. This affects the system profitability of the EH which is further discussed in the 'IEH vs Reference' scenario results. However, this result is influenced by the design of the case study. Therefore, to eliminate the effect of the large-scale exergy destruction, the results for the case only with the sinks with hot water demand is

Fig. 12. Total costs and emissions for existing technologies in 2032.

Fig. 13. Total costs and emissions for existing technologies in 2032 - for sinks with hot water demand.

Fig. 14. Share of excess heat and Natural gas boilers in 2032 for different scenarios.

shown in Fig. 13.

The results in Fig. 13 indicate the reduction in emissions from the use of excess heat in sinks with hot water demand. The use of EH instead of natural gas boilers reduces emissions by about 50 times. Thus, for sinks with hot water demand, the use of EH can significantly reduce emissions notwithstanding the emissions intensity of the grid. However, the emissions illustrated here do not consider the emission associated with the process generating excess heat.

4.1.2. Comparison of scenarios

The 'IEH vs Reference scenario explored the competitiveness of the

EH in comparison to using the existing natural gas-based heating systems, while the emissions penalty scenario introduced a carbon tax based on the current policies in Greece. The subsidy scenario considers a subsidy of 50% in the investment costs of the technologies for excess heat. The share of EH-based heat in the final consumption is used as an indicator of the competitiveness of EH since the ESOM determines the least cost solutions. Fig. 14 shows the share of EH within the system in the different scenarios.

The penetration of EH in the heating system is about 7.6 % in the 'IEH vs Reference' as shown in Fig. 14. The policies to boost the system profitability of the EH are analysed in the emission penalty and subsidy

Fig. 15. Annual heat generation in the sinks for 2032 - 'IEH vs Reference'.

scenarios. The share of excess heat increases to 10.7% when a carbon tax is introduced as shown in Fig. 14. The subsidy in the investment does not affect the penetration of EH to a significant extent. The slight increase in the EH penetration is explained by a relatively small share of the capital investment in the total costs. Due to the large volume of EHR recovery, the operating and variable costs have a dominant share in total costs. In addition, since the EHR technologies are competing with the existing natural gas-based boiler which does not have any capital costs in the model, the reduction of the capital costs only creates a small effect on the cost competitiveness of the EHR technologies.

The EH is only used in the sinks which have a target temperature

same as or lower than the grid temperature as shown in Fig. 15. This is because the sinks that need a higher temperature, use heat pumps, which have a high operating cost due to the use of electricity. Thus, the sinks that use EH are the ones with heat exchangers and the sinks with heat pumps usually meet their heat demand using natural gas boilers. When an emission penalty is introduced, there is an increase in the use of EH in the sinks that use heat exchangers since they do not have any emissions associated as shown in Fig. 16. The sinks that use heat pumps also have associated emissions and hence the introduction of a carbon tax leads to a reduction in the share of excess heat in these sinks.

From the results of the three scenarios, it is observed that the

Fig. 16. Annual heat generation in the sinks for 2032 - emissions case.

emissions penalty scenario creates the largest increase in the share of EH. Furthermore, costs that are associated with the operation of heat generation and EHR technologies have a larger impact on the system rather than the investment costs of the technologies. Thus, a sensitivity analysis is conducted on the costs associated with the operation of the technologies.

Comparing Fig. 15 and Fig. 16, there is an additional penetration of excess heat in 5 sinks all of which use heat exchangers. However, this is once again due to the loss of exergy at the source while conversion leads to the use of temperature boosting technologies. Therefore, to remove the effect of the exergy destruction, the penetration of excess heat for the

sinks with hot water demand is analysed as shown in Fig. 17.

The share of excess heat in sinks with hot water demand is about 40% in the base case and it increases up to 51% with the introduction of emission penalties. The introduction of investment subsidies increases the share of excess heat to 45%. The penetration of excess heat is much higher for sinks with hot water demand. The results highlight the limitation of the method to analyse industrial heat sinks. The limitation arises directly from the inability of the spatial analysis tool to analyse networks other than hot water networks. Therefore, a possible extension of the modelling framework is to further develop it to consider steam networks.

Fig. 17. Comparison of three scenarios - penetration of EH in sinks with hot water demand.

Fig. 18. Share of excess heat in different sensitivity scenarios.

4.1.3. Sensitivity analysis

The variation in the share of EH between the different sensitivity scenarios is shown in Fig. 18. The 100% increase in the carbon tax creates a small effect on the share of EH. It creates a very small increase in the variable costs of the natural gas boilers and thus, it does not increase the competitiveness of IEH relative to the natural gas-based system. However, a 200% increase in the carbon tax increases the share of EH significantly and makes it more cost competitive. A similar result is seen for the increase in natural gas prices. An average natural gas price has already increased the share of EH to 98%. The increase in gas prices has a direct profound effect on the variable costs of the boilers and thus boosts the competitiveness of EH. The share of EH increases by 0.7%

between the average natural gas price and the high natural gas price scenario. The natural gas boiler is used for peak load for a few hours during the year despite the high costs. The ‘best case’ in Fig. 18 represents the scenario with a high gas price of 250 €/MWh and a carbon tax which is a 200% increase on the current taxes. since it has the highest share of EH in the system. Thus, the results from the scenarios are highly sensitive to the variation of the natural gas price and partially sensitive to the increases in carbon taxes. Despite increasing the carbon taxes by 100% and 200%, the results are only partially sensitive since the increase of 100% only causes a small variation in the EH penetration. This is also an indicator of the current low carbon taxes in Greece and how an increase in the taxes could further boost the economic viability of excess

Fig. 19. Sensitivity analysis of natural gas prices in a smaller range.

Fig. 20. Sensitivity analysis of natural gas prices in smaller range for sinks with hot water demand.

Table 11
Installed capacities on the source side.

Source	Technology	Installed capacity in MW
Source 1	Heat exchanger	4.38
Source 4	Heat exchanger	1.15

heat.

The high sensitivity of results to the natural gas price is investigated further by varying the natural gas prices in a smaller range. Since the range of variation of natural gas prices is very high in the sensitivity analysis, it is not possible to determine the shift in optimum. Therefore, the natural gas prices are varied in steps of 10 €/MWh from 50 €/MWh to 100 €/MWh. The results of this sensitivity analysis are shown in Fig. 19.

As seen in Fig. 19, the results are sensitive to the natural gas price in the near range as well. A 20% increase in natural gas prices increases the share of excess heat to 44% from 11%. However, the results are stable until the natural gas price is increased to 100 €/MWh. This increase in the share of excess heat at 60€/MWh is because excess heat becomes

more profitable than natural gas boilers in almost all sinks with hot water demand at this natural gas price. These sinks have heat exchangers instead of heat pumps and thereby have lower investment and operating costs. This is illustrated in Fig. 20.

However, for the sinks with heat pumps, excess heat is not profitable until the natural gas price reaches 100€/MWh. Therefore, the share of excess heat remains constant between 60€/MWh and 90€/MWh. At 100€/MWh, the natural gas boiler is more expensive than heat pumps and therefore there is a shift in the optimum. Hence for the analysed case, there are two shifts in optimum depending on the two types of sink demands.

4.2. Best-case scenario

Based on the results from the sensitivity analysis, the scenario with the largest penetration of EH in the system was determined to be the ‘best-case’ scenario. The case with high natural gas prices and a 200% increase in the current carbon tax rate had the highest EH share of 99.1%.

Sources 1 and 4 are high-temperature sources and hence use heat

Fig. 21. Installed capacities on the sink side for 2032.

exchangers, which have low investment and operating costs thus, investments are made in these sources as shown in Table 11. On the sink side, the installed capacity is quite varied, with combinations of heat pumps, heat exchangers and natural gas boilers as shown in Fig. 21.

The heat generation on the sink side is also quite varied. While heat pumps are used in sinks which require high temperatures, a combination

of heat exchangers and natural gas boilers are used in sinks with temperature requirements lower than the grid temperature. Natural gas boilers are still used to a very small extent, for meeting the peak demand in multiple sinks. The annual heat generation is shown in Fig. 22.

The share of heat supply from the sources is shown in Fig. 23. From the results, the high-temperature sources have been used and are cost-

Fig. 22. Annual heat generation on the sink side for 2032.

competitive compared to the natural gas boilers. The DHCS in the city of Agios-Georgios also uses EH for space heating and hot water demand. As shown in Fig. 22, for Sink 7, stream 1 (hot water) and stream 3 (space heating) are based on EH. However, stream 2 which is space cooling, is still supplied by using electric chillers. Space cooling based on EH using absorption chillers is not shown to be cost-effective according to the results. This is partially due to the reduction in the carbon intensity of electricity in 2032 thereby reducing the effects of a carbon tax on

electricity-based cooling. The country also plans to subsidize electricity-based heating and cooling in the near future and thus, the cost competitiveness of IEH-based cooling is likely to be low in the near term.

The best-case scenario not only presents the case with the highest share of EH but also presents a system design with the lowest emissions. The heat pumps are used in the year 2032 when the emissions from the system are lower and hence the emissions are low despite the use of heat pumps. The reduction of the emission compared to the emission-penalty

Fig. 23. Share of sources in excess heat generation.

Table 12
CO₂ emissions in different scenarios.

Case	Emissions (Tonnes of CO ₂)
Best-case	37
Emission Penalty	9311

scenario is shown in Table 12.

The high variability of the EH has been balanced out by using a hot water tank-based TES in the system. In the best-case scenario, 85 MWh of storage is installed in the model. The storage is continuously operated to average out the variations in supply and demand.

The storage is operated continuously as shown in Fig. 24. The peak storage capacities are used in the winter due to the higher space and water heating demand. However, there is only a small difference between the peak levels of storage in the winter and the summer due to the large share of industrial process heating demand in the total heat demand. The demand for process heat remains almost constant throughout the year and therefore the storage is operated continuously even in the summer months.

The developed method also includes the design of a heating network based on IEH recovery. The designed network is shown in Fig. 25.

In Fig. 25, the red points indicate the sources and the blue points show the sink. The pathways in blue indicate the possible links to connect the sources and the sink, while the path in green is the designed network solution from the spatial analysis tool.

Thus, the results indicate that the system profitability of IEH recovery and use is highly dependent on carbon taxes and the prices of fuels for the existing heating system. However, while considering the future policies and plans based on the country’s NECP, the cost-

competitiveness of IEH increases thereby leading to a large share of IEH recovery in the heat supply mix.

5. Discussion

The developed method is applied to a case study of an industrial park in Greece. The case considers industrial EHR and the supply of heat to industrial sinks for process heating and a neighbouring DHCS for space heating, hot water demand and cooling. The cost-effectiveness of industrial EHR is compared to existing natural gas-based heating systems. The initial comparison between IEH and natural gas-based systems reveals that there is no large difference in heat generation-related emissions between the two options. This is mainly due to the use of heat pumps in the industrial sink when using EH. Since the carbon intensity of electricity is high in Greece for 2022, the emissions from the use of heat pumps are very close to that of using natural gas boilers. However, this result is largely dependent on the design of the case which leads to large-scale destruction of exergy on the source side, thereby leading to the use of temperature-boosting technologies. To eliminate the effect of the exergy destruction, the results for the sinks with hot demands alone were analysed. In this case, the emissions from the use of EH are around 50 times lesser than that of natural gas. However, this does not account for the emission from the process generating EH. A further comparison of the two alternatives based on cost optimization indicates a low share of EH in the heating system when all sinks are considered. These results are further tested in the application of two scenarios for incentivising EH by including carbon taxes and investment subsidies. The two scenarios produce a slightly larger share of EH, with the introduction of a carbon tax increasing the share to a highest of 10.7%. These results tend to vary when only considering sinks with hot water demand, the penetration of excess heat is around 40% in the ‘IEH vs reference’ scenario and it increases to 45% and 51% in the subsidy and emission penalty cases respectively.

The results were further tested using a sensitivity analysis based on a variety of carbon taxation and natural gas prices. The results were extremely sensitive to both carbon taxation and variation in natural gas prices. A 100% increase in taxes increases the share of EH by 80% and an average natural gas price increases the share by 98%. Therefore, the system profitability of EH relies heavily on carbon taxation and the fuel prices for the current heating systems. However, the investment subsidy for EH has a minimal effect on the cost competitiveness of EH.

The results also indicate the limitation of the method in terms of analysing sinks with high-temperature demand such as the industrial sinks with steam demand in the analysed case. The method does not consider the optimisation of the network temperatures based on source and sink temperatures. However, in this case, the maximum possible supply temperature has been considered to reduce the need for

Fig. 24. Storage level in 2032.

Fig. 25. Designed network solution for the best case.

Fig. 26. Overview of the EMB3RS platform modules and their knowledge base.

temperature boosting in industrial sinks. Alternatively, the case could be analysed by considering a steam network to connect high-temperature sources and sinks as highlighted in Section 4.1.2. A steam network can be considered to connect the high-temperature sources directly with the industrial sinks that need steam for process heating. However, the current method cannot consider steam networks due to the limitation that the spatial analysis tool can only consider water-based networks. Therefore, for the best application of the developed method, the case

should analyse the inclusion of excess heat in water-based DHNs. Despite this, the modular design of the current method enables the use of energy system optimisation and the heuristic choice of technology based on exergy analysis without using the spatial analysis tool. Hence, the developed method can be used to analyse steam networks and industrial sinks without analysing the spatial dimension of the network. Nevertheless, the spatial analysis tool must be further developed to analyse high-temperature fluids such as steam and thermal oil for a successful

Fig. 27. Source conversion to the DHN with ORC.

Fig. 28. Source conversion to the DHN with boiler.

Fig. 29. Linearised relation for L2D = 1.

Fig. 30. Linearised relation for L2D = 2.

application of the method to analyse spatial dimensions of high-temperature networks.

The case considers 6 industrial sinks and a DHCS in a neighbouring city to determine the cost-effective amount of IEH that can be used for heating and cooling. The development of the system between the years 2022 and 2032 is analysed. There is the use of EH in all the sinks apart

from the cooling demand. The low carbon intensity of electricity in the year 2032 reduces the impact of carbon taxation on electricity-based cooling and it is more cost-effective than EH-based cooling using absorption chillers. However, this study only considers the comparison between the variable costs of the existing cooling systems against the

Table 13
Robustness of the method.

Case	Iterations needed for convergence
Only IEH scenario	3
IEH vs Reference	2
Emissions penalty	3
Subsidy scenario	2
Sensitivity - carbon tax 100% increase	4
Sensitivity - carbon tax 200% increase	4
Sensitivity - Average gas price	3
Sensitivity - High gas price	4
Sensitivity - Best-case	4

costs of installing and operating absorption chillers. The study does not consider the replacement of the existing cooling systems since they operate well beyond the time period considered for the study. Hence, the results might change if the capital costs of replacing the existing cooling systems are also considered. The results obtained in the case also depend to a large extent on the considered technologies. While several technologies are considered for EH recovery and use, the profitability of EH is compared only against existing natural gas-based heating systems. The results could be different if the comparison is extended to future technologies of decentralized and centralized heating such as solar thermal and small nuclear reactors (SMR). Steam-generating heat pumps have been considered in sinks with steam demand. Due to the large temperature lift in these sinks, the Coefficient of Performance (COP) of these heat pumps is rather low making them unattractive both in terms of cost and emissions. Technical advancements in these technologies could lead to a higher share of heat pumps and EH. In addition, the study considers biomass to be a carbon-neutral source. Although the assumption does not affect the results since there are no investments in biomass boilers, the supply chain of biomass and the associated emission could be considered for a comprehensive analysis. Furthermore, the sensitivity for the gas prices is based on the high price of gas in Europe since the second quarter of 2022. The final achieved share of EH could vary based on the variation in gas prices. Thus, this case specifically considers the application of the developed method to a case of industrial EHR for industrial symbiosis and use in DHCS based on a comparison with existing technologies. The case can be extended in various dimensions by increasing the number of comparative technologies, extending the model horizon, and adding more IEH sources and sinks to the analysed case and the developed method can be further used to analyse each of these cases or other cases of industrial EHR.

The developed method of creating a link between three special-purpose tools provides a comprehensive and practical design of a heating grid based on industrial EHR. The application of the method to the case study and the several scenarios indicates the robustness of the methods. Convergence was achieved within a maximum of 4 iterations in all cases. While a combined optimization of the heating network and capacity investment design by hard linking the two tools would lead to an earlier convergence, the computational requirements of such a tool would be immense. The developed method can be used to provide a long-term investment plan for industrial stakeholders for implementing EHR projects. The results from the modelling framework provide the stakeholder, the cost-optimal capacities and operation of EHR technologies, and the cost-optimal network layout. This helps eliminate the lack of information within the industries and overcome the general and technical barriers to EHR. While the stride toward quantum computing is still in its initial stages, the soft linking of tools in an iterative manner provides the best chance of obtaining accurate and practical results within current computational limitations.

The developed method can further be extended to conduct a long-term analysis in the ESOM while complementing it with a dispatch model to verify the feasibility of the proposed long-term solution. The ESOM used in the current study can optimise the investments in the system over a longer horizon, i.e., 40 or 50 years. Such an analysis would

be conducted from the perspective of a DHS operator rather than an industrial stakeholder. Nevertheless, the insights from the analysis could be useful for long-term planning for the development of industries. However, conducting such an analysis at an hourly time resolution would again require massive computational resources. Thus, the long-term analysis can still be conducted at a low time resolution than hourly even while considering sample years, while establishing an iterative feasibility link with a dispatch model to determine feasibility and provide the dispatch to the spatial analysis tool. This further boosts the practicality of results while considering long-term perspectives to establish investment plans for industries and DHCS operators.

6. Conclusion

The study explores the cost-effective share of IEH in a heating system based on a novel method to capture the various aspects of industrial EHR. The method considers using an exergy analysis tool to determine the exergy potential of using EH. The calculated technical potentials are fed into an ESOM and a spatial analysis tool. An iterative soft link is proposed between the ESOM and the spatial analysis tool to obtain a comprehensive network design while considering the optimal dispatch and an optimal design of system capacity while considering the actual losses in the network.

The developed method is applied to a case of industrial EHR to analyse the recovery of IEH and use in industries for process heat and hot water, space heating and cooling in a DHCS. Five scenarios are analysed to consider the system profitability and emission reduction from the use of IEH. The scenarios indicate that the emission reduction from using IEH is dependent to a large extent on the emission intensity of the electricity grid due to the use of heat pumps to increase the temperature of the heat. The scenarios also indicate that the system profitability of EH is low for the analysed case in the current policy setting, but this result is extremely sensitive to carbon pricing and an increase in natural gas prices. Increased natural gas prices and higher carbon taxes seem inevitable in the future thereby making EHR more attractive to industries.

While the study considers a specific method for assessing industrial EHR and the application to a specific case study, the results of the study also indicate the larger system benefits of using industrial EHR in terms of emission reductions. Incentivising industrial EHR reduces the need to reduce energy consumption and adopt sustainable consumption. Therefore, more energy is consumed, and the excess is recovered leading to a reduction in overall system efficiency. Thus, future modelling studies should also associate the cost of excess energy use and thereby the reduction in overall energy efficiency. The study also highlights the role of policy regulations such as carbon taxation to boost the cost-effectiveness of industrial EHR in the future. The modelling framework developed in this study can capture the three technical barriers, temporal, spatial and temperature mismatch of EHR. Furthermore, cost optimisation and long-term planning provide investment pathways and financial indicators for decision-making at an industrial level. Therefore, the application of the method can help solve the lack of information in decision-making. However, there are other regulatory and societal barriers such as lack of transparency in the contract between DHS operators and industries, reliability of heat supply from EHR etc. that are not considered in this study. Another direct indication from this study is to enhance further development of multi-model and inter-operable toolkits. Such toolkits can assist to make important investment decisions with the support of a portfolio of modelling analyses looking at the different perspectives of the problem. This helps to contextualize the results of the models and present them in terms that can be interpreted by industrial stakeholders and policymakers.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Shravan Kumar: Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing –

original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Jagruti Thakur**: Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration. **José Maria Cunha**: Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Francesco Gardumi**: Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Ali Kök**: Methodology, Writing – original draft. **André Lisboa**: Conceptualization, Methodology. **Viktoria Martin**: Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – review & editing, Supervision.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix 1

The EMB3RS platform, a planning tool for matching sources and sinks

The EMB3RS platform is designed as a simple matchmaking tool that addresses the key requirements when planning a new DHN or expanding an existing DHN, focusing on the use of industrial surplus heat [32]. The platform, which is still under development, will assess potential sinks for sources with available surplus heat or vice versa, depending on user requirements.

Industrial users that have significant amounts of surplus heat will provide essential parameters, such as their location and the characteristics of the available surplus heat. The EMB3RS platform will then autonomously and intuitively evaluate the feasibility of new business scenarios and identify technical solutions. End users, such as energy communities, will be able to determine the costs and benefits of industrial surplus heat and cold use routes and define the requirements for implementing the most promising solutions. Bringing together surplus heat providers and end users will enable partnerships that benefit both parties and reduce CO₂ emissions.

To date, some platforms map the potential for installing a new DHN based on land density and building type, such as the Hotmaps project [53]. However, these platforms do not perform pipeline routing optimization or detailed analysis of the mismatch between the sink and source profiles. Other platforms, such as the THERMOS platform [54], provide automatic pipe routing for a given area on an open street map and perform analysis based on total annual heat demand and peak demand, although there is no detailed analysis of the mismatch between the sink and source profiles.

The EMB3RS platform, when completed, shall perform the following list of actions:

- Mapping of heat/cold sources and sinks.
- Calculation of the distance between sources and sinks.
- Automatic routing of pipelines.
- Calculation of heat losses in the network based on the distance between sources and sinks and their temperature levels.

- Calculation of costs for installation/construction of the network.
- Cost of integrating surplus heat/cooling into a district heating/district cooling network.
- Cost of integrating surplus heat/cooling into on-site processes.
- Savings in energy sources and associated expenses from using surplus heat and cooling.
- Calculation of economic impact (revenues and costs) for all actors involved in the energy community, e.g., supermarkets and consumers.
- CO₂ reduction using surplus heat/cold.
- Cost of converting surplus heat into electricity.

The platform is divided into five modules and a knowledge base, as shown in Fig. 26. The knowledge base will be a dynamic database that will provide reference values (and default generation and demand profiles) for the different modules to use in their simulations. These include specific equipment costs, expected equipment efficiencies, fuel and electricity costs, DHN costs, heat exchanger characterization and associated costs, etc.).

Appendix 2

Conversions for Organic Rankine Cycle and Boilers.

The circuit for the ORC technology on the sink side is shown in Fig. 27.

The circuit for boilers on the source side is shown in Fig. 28.

Appendix 3

Linear regression for the relation between storage surface area and storage capacity

Since the non-linear relation between storage surface area and the storage capacity cannot be modelled in a linear program-based model, a regression was considered in Excel to linearise the relationship. Two L2D ratios have been considered as explained in Section 2.3. Thermal storage tanks with capacities between 0 and 5000 GJ have been used for the regression. The relationship between the storage surface area and the storage capacity. Fig. 29 and Fig. 30 show the relationship and the linear regression for the two L2D ratios.

As shown in Fig. 29 and Fig. 30, the linear relation between the surface area and the capacity produces a value for the coefficient of determination close to 1 indicating the regression covers all the variability of the data around its mean.

Appendix 4

Robustness of method

The developed method analyses the different aspects of designing a heating grid based on IEH. An iterative soft link between an ESOM and a spatial analysis tool is proposed to capture the losses in the grid and design accurate pipe capacities based on dispatch. The iterative link is tested using the case study in different scenarios. The robustness of the method is determined by whether convergence is achieved in these iterations and how many iterations are needed to achieve convergence in each case as shown in Table 13.

The cases with low penetration of IEH need only 2 iterations for convergence since the dispatch of IEH is very low and there is not much variation in the dispatch between the iterations. However, in the cases with a higher penetration of excess heat, the ESOM optimises the dispatch of excess heat between the different sources and thus the change in the dispatch based on the losses is much larger in each iteration. Therefore, the number of iterations to achieve convergence

depends on the possibility of variation in the dispatch. The method has been tested with a case of 4 sources and 7 sinks and a maximum of 4 iterations is needed for convergence. However, the number of iterations could increase if more sources or sinks are included since it increases the possibility for variations in the dispatch and hence the losses.

The simulation using the proposed modelling framework was conducted on a desktop computer with 256 GB memory, and a processor with the specification 3.50 GHz, 3492 MHz, 4 Core(s), and 8 Logical Processor(s). The spatial and techno-economic optimizations were conducted using Gurobipy. The simulation time for a run of 3 iterations was 3 h and 10 min and for a run of 4 iterations was 4 h.

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